

Enhancements to Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein Distributions Based on Reaction Balance?

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In this note, we consider small enhancements to the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein distributions based on reaction balance. For fermions, reaction balance for

$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ ((1)) leads to:

$$f(e_1)[1-f(e_3)] f(e_2)[1-f(e_4)] = f(e_3)[1-f(e_1)] f(e_4)[1-f(e_2)] \quad ((2))$$

Taking \ln of ((2)) and equating to ((1)) yields the Fermi-Dirac distribution. In ((2)), $[1-f(e_3)]$ represents average Pauli blocking of e_1 from entering e_3 . $[1-f(e_3)]$ is an average value and so it seems ((2)) is an approximation. This approximation may be shown to be equivalent to that of the grand canonical partition function. If one applies reaction balance to small particle number systems (1), one may calculate more accurate Pauli blocking, it seems. We try to apply some of these ideas to the average expression ((2)) to see if a modification may be obtained. A modification is also attempted for the Bose-Einstein distribution.

Generalized Reaction Balances

We have argued in previous notes, that statistical mechanics is based on reactions. For example, one may have $f(e_i)$ representing the number of particles in state e_i , but the probability for an e_i particle to react may not be proportional to $f(e_i)$ as in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case. Even the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases consider $f(e_i)$ as a main factor in the probability to react, but then modify them by the factors $[1-f(e_j)]$ (fermions) or $[1+f(e_j)]$ (boson enhancement) for e_i scattering into e_j . Thus, we argue that for generalized scattering:

$$g(f(e_1)) [1 -/+ f(e_3)] g(f(e_2) [1 -/+ f(e_4)] = g(f(e_3))[1-f(e_1)] g(f(e_4)) [1-f(e_1)] \quad ((3))$$

where - fermions + bosons

Taking \ln of ((3)) and equating to ((1)) (conservation of energy) yields:

$$\ln \{g(f(e_i)) / [1 -/+ f(e_i)]\} = -(e_i - u)/T \text{ where } u \text{ and } T \text{ are constants} \quad ((4))$$

For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, $g = \text{identity function}$ and one obtains the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein distributions.

Kaniadakis (2) has defined an entropy density by: $\int df \ln\{g(f(e_i)) / [1 -/+ f(e_i)]\} \quad ((5))$

Using this, together with $E-TS+uN$ yields a function proportional to the \ln of the grand partition function. Thus, reaction balance used in ((4)) with factors such as $[1-f(e_i)]$ is also an approximation at the level of the grand partition function approximation.

The grand partition function applies to large particle numbers, thus it seems reaction balance as given by ((4)) (i.e. using $[1-f(e_j)]$) also applies to large numbers.

Small Particle Number Equilibrium

In (1), we examined the case of two electrons in three equally spaced levels e_g , e_1 and e_3 where $e_g=e_{\text{ground}}$. For this case, one may consider three scenarios:

N1 1 electron in e_3 1 electron in e_1 0 electron in e_g
 N2 1 electron in e_3 0 electrons in e_1 1 electron in e_g
 N3 0 electrons in e_3 1 electron in e_1 1 electron in e_g

We tried to calculate scattering balances by balancing reactions from N1 to N3 with those of N3 to N1 etc. Two types of calculations were performed. In one, having an electron in a state indicates that another electron may not scatter into this same state by Pauli blocking. In the second case, we considered an electron in a state moving out at the same time another electron moves in. This second process includes lower probabilities (more small factors), but possibly may be applied to the average case in of large numbers given in ((4)). In other words, one adds dynamics to particle states.

Enhancement to the Fermi-Dirac Distribution

In ((4)), the factor $[1-f(e_j)]$ is used to describe average Pauli blocking. A particle in state e_j is present $f(e_j)$ of the time, so $1-f(e_j)$ of the time it is absent and e_i may enter state e_j . One may try to modify this two ways. In general, $f(e_j) < 1$, but is not a probability because $\text{Sum over } j f(e_j) = N$, the number of particles in a system. For a single level, say j , however, $f(e_j)$ does seem to act like a probability because there is an $f(e_j)$ chance that the particle is there and a $(1-f(e_j))$ that it is not.

Consider an equilibrium situation in which $f(e_j)$ does not change in time. Then:

$(1-f(e_j)) P_{in} - f(e_j) P_{out} = 0$ where P_{in} and P_{out} are the probabilities to enter and leave state e_j

A solution is: $P_{in}=f(e_j)$ and $P_{out}=1-f(e_j)$

Next, consider three scenarios:

- A. e_i tries to scatter into an empty e_j and no other particle tries to scatter into e_j at the same time. The reaction will occur.

- B. e_i tries to scatter into an empty e_j , but another particle also tries to scatter in. It seems one might try to argue the reaction occurs some of the time depending on which particle is blocked. Let X be the probability that e_i gets in first.
- C. e_i tries to scatter into an occupied e_j at the same time the e_j particle is leaving. The reaction occurs.

Then:

$$f(e_i) \{ [1-f(e_j)] \{ 1 - P_{out} f(e_j)/[1-f(e_j)] \} + f(e_i)f(e_j) P_{out} \} \text{ scenarios A and C} = f(e_i)[1-f(e_j)]$$

$$\text{Scenario B gives } f(e_i)(1-f(e_j))P_{in} X = f(e_i)[1-f(e_j)] f(e_j)X \quad ((6))$$

Thus, in a reaction balance, $g(e_i)[1-f(e_j)]$ is replaced with:

$$g(e_i) \{ [1-f(e_j)] + [1-f(e_j)] f(e_j)X \} \quad ((7))$$

$f(e_j) < 1$ so the second term in ((7)) is the correction due to dynamics. X as well is less than 1.

In other words, the reaction is enhanced and ((4)) becomes:

$$\text{Ln} [g(e_i) / \{ [1-f(e_i)] [1 + f(e_i)X] \}] = -(e_i - u)/T \quad ((8))$$

For Maxwell-Boltzmann type scattering g is the identity function:

$$\text{Ln} [f(e_i) / \{ [1-f(e_i)] [1 + f(e_i)X] \}] = -(e_i - u)/T \quad ((8))$$

One has:

$$f = a(1-f)(1+fX) \quad ((9a))$$

If f were to become small relative to 1 then $f = a$ which is the Maxwell-Boltzmann result. For $X=0$, one has the usual Fermi-Dirac result.

$$0 = a + f(aX - a - 1) - aX f^2 \quad \text{Where } a = \exp(-(e_i - u)/T).$$

Solving yields:

$$f_{\text{Fermi-Dirac enhanced}} = (-aX+a+1)/(-2aX) - 1/(-2aX) \sqrt{(ax-a-1)^2 + 4a^*aX} \quad ((9b))$$

Where $a = \exp(-(e_i - u)/T)$

X is the probability for an e_i to make it into the state e_j if another particle is also trying to enter the same state. One may try various numbers such $\frac{1}{2}$ etc.

Enhancement to the Bose-Einstein Distribution

For the Bose-Einstein distribution, $f(e_j)$ may be larger than 1. It counts the number of particles in a state e_j . A particle in e_i , however, may undergo many kinds of collisions, with only a portion leading to the creation of an e_j . Thus, $f(e_i)/A$ is the probability for a reaction to lead to an e_j and this must be multiplied by the boson enhancement factor. The boson enhancement, however, i.e. adding an extra e_j boson to a state e_j with $f(e_j)$ bosons is $1+f(e_j)$ without normalization.

The expression $f(e_i)(1+f(e_j))$ is proportional to the probability for a particle e_i to scatter into e_j when e_j has $f(e_j)$ particles. This expression may describe an e_i scattering into e_j (where the state e_j is static), or an e_i scattering into e_j at the same time that one particle is leaving e_j and another entering, or two leaving two entering etc.

Enhancement scenarios may include e_i entering e_j as an e_j is leaving or e_i entering e_j as another particle enters e_j . Thus, the enhancement tries to capture dynamics.

Consider:

- A. A particle tries to move out of e_j as e_i comes in. Then the probability is

$$f(e_i) f(e_j) f(e_j)/B \quad \text{where } 1/B \text{ is the probability for any reaction to occur.} \quad ((10))$$

The first $f(e_j)$ indicates that the boson enhancement is $f(e_j)$ and not $f(e_j)+1$ in this case. One might argue that two particles, or three etc come out, but it seems that these would involve more and more factors of $f(e_j)/A$ which would be increasingly small.

- B. A particle tries to move into e_j as e_i also moves in. The probability is postulated to be:

$$\text{Sum over } k \quad f(e_i)[2+f(e_j)] [2+f(e_j)] f(e_k) (1/BA) = f(e_i)[2+f(e_j)] [2+f(e_j)] N/(BA) \quad ((11))$$

$f(e_i)[2+f(e_j)]$ is proportional to the probability for $f(e_i)$ to scatter into e_j . A particle e_k , also sees the enhancement of $[2+f(e_j)]$ and the factor $1/A$ indicates that e_k may react in many ways that do not move it into e_j . For example, if e_k and e_l interact, one may have:

$$e_k + e_l = e_j + e_m \quad \text{or} \quad e_k + e_l = e_p + e_q \quad \text{where } p \neq j \text{ and } q \neq j$$

1/B is the probability for any reaction to occur. For example, e_k does not have to scatter in a time dt .

The overall effect is $f(e_i)[1+f(e_j)] + f(e_i) f(e_j) f(e_j)1/B + f(e_i)[2+f(e_j)] [2+f(e_j)] N/(BA)$ ((12))

which is suggestive of a quadratic equation in f .

The question now becomes how to evaluate 1/B and 1/A. An alternative approach is:

$f(e_j)$ is constant in time so: $[Rate\ into\ e_j - Rate\ out\ of\ e_j] dt=0$ or

$[1+f(e_j)] Pin - Pout =0$ and ((12)) may be written as:

$f(e_i)[1+f(e_j)] + f(e_i)f(e_j) Pout + f(e_i)[2+f(e_j)][2+f(e_j)] Pin$ or

$f(e_i)[1+f(e_j)] + f(e_i)f(e_j) Pout(e_j) + f(e_i)[2+f(e_j)][2+f(e_j)] Pout(e_j)/ [1+f(e_j)]$ ((13))

$Pout$ is the probability a particle with e_j will scatter out of e_j . This should be related to the cross section, the density of particles and the flux of e_j all multiplied by the number of particles in e_j i.e. $f(e_j)$. It should also be noted that for e_j , each change into an e_i brings a boson enhancement factor of $(f(e_i)+1)$. Thus, $Pout(e_j)$ should be obtainable, but is not particularly simple to obtain. Using ((13)), one may at least obtain a sense of a possible correction to the Bose-Einstein distribution as:

$f(e_i) / \{1+f(e_i)+ f(e_i)Pout(e_i) + [2+f(e_i)][2+f(e_i)] / [1+f(e_i)] Pout(e_i)\} = \exp(-(e_i-u)/T)$ ((14a))

It seems that $Pout(e_i)$ may be proportional to $f(e_i)$ the number of particles in e_i so $Pout(e_i)=f(e_i)P1out(e_i)$. Then ((14a)) becomes:

$f(e_i) / \{1+f(e_i)+ f(e_i)f(e_i)P1out(e_i) + \{ [2+f(e_i)][2+f(e_i)] / [1+f(e_i)]\} f(e_i) P1out(e_i)\} = \exp(-(e_i-u)/T)$ ((14b))

This leads to a cubic equation (which in principle may be solved analytically), but for simplicity, we approximate $f(e_j)/[1+f(e_i)]=1$. Then one obtains the approximate quadratic equation:

$0 = f^*f [2Pa] + f [-1+a +5Pa] + [a+4Pa]$ where $P=P1out(e_i)$ and $a=\exp(-(e_i-u)/T)$ ((15))

Thus:

$f\ Bose\ Einstein\ enhanced = [1-a-5Pa]/[4Pa] - 1/[4Pa] \sqrt{[1-2a+a^*a-7P^*Pa^*a-10Pa+2Pa^*a]}$ ((16))

Where $a=\exp(-(e-u)/T)$ for $f/(1+f)$ close to 1. For smaller f values, one may solve the cubic equation ((14b))

The - sign is chosen by requiring that f become the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution (or similar to it) when a becomes very small.

Conclusion

In this somewhat hand-wavy note, we try to add dynamics into fermion and boson scattering and apply this to the reaction balance approach of statistical mechanics in order to find enhancements to the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein distributions. If one uses a generalized scattering approach for which $\ln(g(f(e))) = -(e-u)/T$ with $g=f/(1-f)$ and $g=f/(1+f)$ for fermions and bosons, this approach applies to large particle number systems and is equivalent in accuracy to the grand canonical partition function approach. It seems, however, that reaction balance may be applied to systems with small particle numbers, but then one must balance all reactions. In doing so, one encounters various dynamic scenarios which one may try to apply to the large number average reaction balance in order to provide enhancements. The enhanced fermion and boson distributions found in this note are given by: ((9)) and ((16))

References:

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